
D1.1 – Data and ethics management plan and guidelines

***Promoting Opportunities for Wide-scale Energy Renewal:
Unlocking Potential***

**D1.1 – Data and ethics management plan
and guidelines**

Authors:

**Óscar PRETEL (CIMNE),
Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)**

February, 2026 (M04) – WP1, D1.1

Funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement nº 101235894. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Technical References

Project Acronym	POWERUP
Project Title	Promoting Opportunities for Wide-scale Energy Renewal Unlocking Potential

Deliverable No. & Title	D1.1 – Data and ethics management plan and guidelines
Type of deliverable	R (document, report)
Dissemination Level	PUBLIC
Work Package	WP1 – Project Management 1
Lead beneficiary	01 (CIMNE)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	02 (ICAEN)
Due date of deliverable	28 February 2026
Actual submission date	26 February 2026

Authors	Oscar PRETEL (CIMNE), Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
Contributors	Arnau ALIANA (ICAEN)

Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
V1	20/01/26	Table of Content	Óscar PRETEL (CIMNE)
V2	30/01/26	Initial draft	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
V3	02/02/26	Full draft	Óscar PRETEL (CIMNE)
V4	06/02/26	Revision and formatting	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)
V5	12/02/26	Peer-review	Arnau ALIANA (ICAEN)
V6	13/02/26	Final version of deliverable	Gerard LAGUNA (CIMNE)

Content

1	Introduction	9
1.1	Scope	10
1.2	Guiding principles for data management	10
1.3	Legal and ethical context	12
1.3.1	<i>Data protection and data governance regulations</i>	12
1.3.1.1	<i>General data protection Regulation (GDPR)(EU2016/679)</i>	12
1.3.1.2	<i>The sharing of non-personal data: EU Regulation 2807/2018</i>	13
1.3.1.3	<i>Privacy and Electronic communications directive: EC 2002/58</i>	13
1.3.1.4	<i>Legal nature of data and IP issues: ownership, protection of database and trade secrets</i>	13
1.3.1.5	<i>Legislation on open data: (EU) 2019/1024</i>	13
1.3.1.6	<i>National data protection regulations</i>	14
1.3.1.7	<i>Cybersecurity regulations and risk management</i>	14
1.3.2	<i>Ethical Guidelines and best practices</i>	14
1.3.2.1	<i>AI and data ethics</i>	14
1.3.2.2	<i>Ethical Research involving Humans</i>	15
1.3.2.3	<i>Gender equality and inclusivity</i>	15
2	Data Management Plan (DMP)	16
2.1	Data summary	16
2.1.1	<i>Type and format of data that will be generated/collected</i>	16
2.2	Data management	17
2.2.1	<i>Participants and personal data</i>	18
2.2.1.1	<i>Data collected from surveys</i>	18
2.2.1.2	<i>Data collected from interviews and focus group</i>	19
2.2.1.3	<i>Photography or filming in events</i>	19
2.2.1.4	<i>POWERUP privacy policy</i>	20
2.2.2	<i>Providers and proprietary data</i>	20
2.2.3	<i>Data protection and personal data governance</i>	21
2.2.3.1	<i>Lawful Basis for data processing</i>	21
2.2.3.2	<i>Informed consent</i>	21
2.2.3.3	<i>Data minimisation</i>	21

2.2.3.4	<i>Legitimate interest</i>	22
2.2.3.5	<i>Data security and protection measures</i>	22
2.2.3.6	<i>Data protection officer</i>	22
2.2.3.7	<i>Roles: Data controller and processor</i>	22
2.2.4	<i>Dissemination, open access and protection of results</i>	22
2.2.5	<i>Open Science and FAIR data implementation</i>	23
2.2.5.1	<i>Making data findable, including provisions for metadata</i>	24
2.2.5.2	<i>Making data accessible</i>	25
2.2.5.3	<i>Making data interoperable</i>	26
2.2.5.4	<i>Making data re-use</i>	26
2.2.6	<i>Intellectual property rights</i>	26
2.2.6.1	<i>Background IPR</i>	26
2.2.6.2	<i>Foreground results and IPR from the project</i>	27
2.2.6.3	<i>Access rights and confidentiality</i>	27
2.2.7	<i>Licenses</i>	27
2.2.8	<i>Data retention and long-term preservation</i>	27
2.2.8.1	<i>Public data (anonymous)</i>	28
2.2.8.2	<i>Public data (non-anonymous)</i>	28
2.3	<i>Data anonymization and pseudonymization</i>	29
2.3.1	<i>Anonymization strategies</i>	29
2.3.2	<i>Pseudonymization strategies</i>	29
3	Ethical research framework	30
3.1	EU code of conduct for research integrity	30
3.2	The principle of proportionality	31
3.3	Gender equality	31
3.4	AI Ethics.....	32
4	Conclusion	33
	Annexes	34
	ANNEX 1. Informed consent form for participating in surveys	34
	ANNEX 2. Consent form for interviews and focus groups.....	35
	ANNEX 3: Consent form for photography or filming.....	37

Executive summary

The POWERUP project is co-funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe programme. POWERUP aims to support the fair, socially acceptable, and sustainable deployment of renewable energy sources (RES) across European regions by strengthening governance frameworks, stakeholder engagement, and evidence-based decision-making through coordination, analysis, and methodological support.

This document is Deliverable D1.1 – Data and Ethics Management Plan and Guidelines. It defines the framework governing the responsible management of research data and the ethical conduct of all project activities throughout the project lifecycle.

This deliverable outlines the ethical, legal, and technical framework for managing research data and ensuring ethical compliance within the POWERUP project. It establishes procedures for data collection, processing, storage, sharing, retention, and deletion, with particular emphasis on the protection of personal and sensitive information in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other applicable European and national regulations.

The Data Management Plan provides a comprehensive approach to data management across the project's work packages, reflecting the nature of POWERUP as a Coordination and Support Action (CSA). It identifies the categories of data generated or collected, including qualitative, quantitative, aggregated, and publicly available data, and defines measures for data protection, controlled access, sharing, and long-term preservation. Clear protocols are established to ensure participant privacy, confidentiality, and compliance with ethical and legal requirements.

In line with Horizon Europe open science obligations, the plan implements the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) to enhance transparency and accessibility of non-sensitive research outputs. A dedicated POWERUP project community in Zenodo is established as the main repository for open-access deliverables, publications, and associated metadata, supporting standardisation and long-term preservation.

The ethical research framework described in this document ensures compliance with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and relevant EU ethical standards. It emphasises the principles of reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability across all research, coordination, stakeholder engagement, and dissemination activities carried out within the project.

This Data and Ethics Management Plan is a living document, which will be reviewed and updated at Months 18 and 36 to maintain its relevance and effectiveness as the project evolves. It serves as a key reference for all POWERUP partners, ensuring the consistent and compliant application of data management and ethical principles across all project activities.

List of Tables

Table 1. Abbreviations and acronyms	8
Table 2. Data related to the Work Package	17
Table 3. Zenodo’s metadata generated	24
Table 4. Zenodo’s metadata overview	25

List of Figures

Figure 1. Data flow	12
---------------------------	----

Table 1. Abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BC	Business Case
BEMS	Building Energy Management Systems
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
DMP	Data Management Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUPL	European Union Public License
EV	Electric Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
HVAC	Heating, Ventilating and Air Conditioning
ICT	Information & Communication Technologies
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MS	Milestones
PV	Photovoltaic
UBFlex	Universal Building Flexibility Interface
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This document presents the Data and Ethics Management Plan (DEMP) for the POWERUP project. Its purpose is to define the principles, procedures, and responsibilities governing the collection, processing, storage, sharing, protection, and ethical use of data generated or collected throughout the project lifecycle, in accordance with Horizon Europe requirements and applicable legal and ethical frameworks.

POWERUP is a Coordination and Support Action that develops and validates methodologies and open tools to support the socially acceptable and fair deployment of renewable energy sources (RES) across European regions. In order to achieve its objectives, the project involves a wide range of data-related activities embedded across several work packages, including analytical, participatory, digital, and dissemination-oriented tasks.

The project does not develop, deploy, or operate technical systems or infrastructures, but focuses on coordination, analysis, stakeholder engagement, methodological development, and support to policy and decision-making processes.

The Data and Ethics Management Plan applies to all project partners and affiliated entities and covers all data processing activities carried out within the scope of the project.

The expected data-related activities within the project are:

- In particular, data generation and processing activities are foreseen in the following types of tasks, as defined in the project proposal (Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement)
- Contextual and socio-economic analysis tasks (WP3), involving the collection and analysis of qualitative and quantitative data related to regional energy contexts, governance structures, stakeholder landscapes, and social acceptability aspects of RES deployment.
- Development of digital and decision-support tools (WP4 and WP5), including a GIS-based decision support tool and associated datasets. These tasks involve the use of geospatial data, technical parameters, aggregated indicators, and non-personal data sourced from public databases and project analyses.
- Stakeholder engagement, co-creation, and validation activities (WP6), including workshops, surveys, interviews, and participatory processes with public authorities, energy agencies, citizens, and other stakeholders. These tasks may involve the processing of limited personal data (e.g. professional role, organisation, region, feedback and opinions).
- Replication and sustainability activities (WP7), which rely on structured data, lessons learned, and anonymised feedback from pilot and follower regions to support transferability and upscaling.
- Communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities (WP8 and WP9), including the management of project communication channels, event organisation, mailing lists, and dissemination materials, which may involve the processing of contact details and audiovisual content, always subject to consent and data protection requirements.

Across these tasks, POWERUP primarily processes non-personal, aggregated, and anonymised data. Where personal data are involved, they are limited in scope, processed only when necessary for the implementation of the action, and handled in full compliance with the GDPR and relevant national legislation.

1.1 Scope

The document is intended for use by all project participants who are responsible or in any way involved in the data collection in order to guide them in the handling, storage and processing of the data. The document aims also to provide transparency of the data management process and the implementation of the data protection procedures for the stakeholders involved in the project pilot activities and other relevant stakeholders interested in the adoption of the project solution.

The scope of this plan includes:

- Data generated or collected during project analysis, tool development, validation, replication, and dissemination activities.
- Limited personal data related to stakeholders participating in workshops, surveys, interviews, and events.
- Non-personal, aggregated, and geospatial data used for analytical and decision-support purposes.
- Ethical considerations related to stakeholder engagement, gender equality, inclusiveness, and the responsible use of digital and AI-supported tools.

1.2 Guiding principles for data management

The data management in POWERUP is an end-to-end process that includes the phases of collection, processing, generation and sharing of data throughout the project duration and beyond. Almost half of the deliverables (10 out of 22) are classified as sensitive and therefore must be handled under this protection category. The remaining deliverables will be openly accessible and will allow the establishment of the necessary processes for decision-making, implementation, and the subsequent use of these documents and data. The rest of the deliverables are public and open.

POWERUP intends to collect and analyse data from multiple distributed sources related to regional energy contexts, governance frameworks, stakeholder engagement activities, and the social acceptability of renewable energy deployment across participating regions. These data support the development of methodologies, analytical tools, and guidelines aimed at facilitating fair and socially acceptable large-scale renewable energy uptake.

All data handled within POWERUP are considered research data and may be collected manually or automatically through project activities such as surveys, workshops, interviews, desk research, and the use of publicly available datasets. Personal data provided by individual participants or organisations are not shared at an individual level outside the responsible partner. Only anonymised and aggregated data

are used for analysis, reporting, and dissemination purposes, ensuring that individuals cannot be identified and that sensitive information is adequately protected.

The guiding principles are the following:

- **Lawfulness, fairness and transparency:** All data processing activities are carried out in compliance with applicable EU and national legislation, in particular the GDPR. Data subjects are clearly informed about the purpose, scope, and conditions of data processing, ensuring transparency and fairness.
- **Purpose limitation:** Data are collected and processed solely for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes directly related to the implementation of the POWERUP project, as defined in the Grant Agreement and Description of the Action.
- **Data minimisation and proportionality:** Only data that are strictly necessary to achieve the project objectives are collected and processed. The scope and level of detail of data collection are proportionate to the nature of the activities and the associated ethical and legal risks.
- **Accuracy and quality:** Reasonable measures are taken to ensure that data are accurate, relevant, and, where necessary, kept up to date, supporting the reliability of analyses, tools, and project outputs.
- **Integrity and confidentiality:** Data are protected against unauthorised access, alteration, loss, or disclosure through appropriate technical and organisational security measures. Access to data is restricted to authorised persons on a need-to-know basis.
- **Accountability and responsibility:** Each project partner is responsible for ensuring compliance with data protection and data management obligations for the data under its control, in line with its role as data controller or data processor.
- **Ethics-by-design and privacy-by-design:** Ethical considerations and data protection safeguards are integrated from the earliest stages of activity design, ensuring respect for fundamental rights, autonomy of participants, and trust in project outcomes.
- **FAIR principles for non-sensitive data:** Where applicable and feasible, non-personal and non-sensitive data generated within POWERUP are managed according to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), supporting transparency, reuse, and impact, without compromising confidentiality or legitimate interests.
- **Open science and responsible dissemination:** POWERUP support open access to research outputs and data sharing in line with Horizon Europe open science policies, while balancing openness with data protection, intellectual property rights, and confidentiality requirements.
- **Security and risk management:** Data management includes continuous assessment of potential risks related to data processing and the implementation of appropriate mitigation measures, including cybersecurity best practices.

These guiding principles constitute the foundation for all data-related activities in POWERUP and are operationalised through the procedures and measures described in the subsequent sections of this Data and Ethics Management Plan. The data management processes are represented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Data flow

To protect the privacy of individual participants or organizations, only data that can be irreversibly anonymised to the degree that it is impossible to identify individuals will be shared publicly. Non-anonymised data will be kept internally in the project and used as input to project work, but never shared publicly in its original format. Both the anonymised and non-anonymised data will, in an aggregated format, feed into project work and provide the basis for analysis in deliverables and publications. If the editor of a deliverable is concerned that their deliverable contains personal information, they can request a separate screening for privacy and ethics issues before submission to be sure that no personal data is included. Public deliverables, publications and anonymised datasets will be shared openly through open research data repositories described in 2.2.5 Open Science and FAIR data implementation.

During the lifetime of the project, partners might discover special parts of the project's results that should be protected for further developments or commercial exploitation. If these cases arise, appropriate steps to protect such results for exploitation purposes will be taken.

1.3 Legal and ethical context

POWERUP complies with all relevant EU, international, and national legal frameworks governing data protection, data governance, ethics, and research integrity.

1.3.1 Data protection and data governance regulations

1.3.1.1 General data protection Regulation (GDPR)(EU2016/679)

The GDPR establishes the legal framework for the protection of personal data within the European Union. It defines principles for lawful data processing, the rights of data subjects, and the obligations of data controllers and processors. Within POWERUP, the GDPR governs the processing of any personal data

related to stakeholders, event participants, and communication activities, ensuring transparency, data minimisation, security, and accountability.¹

1.3.1.2 The sharing of non-personal data: EU Regulation 2807/2018

This regulation ensures the free flow of non-personal data² across EU Member States by prohibiting unjustified data localisation requirements. It supports cross-border cooperation and data-driven innovation. POWERUP applies this regulation when handling aggregated, technical, or geospatial data that do not qualify as personal data³.

1.3.1.3 Privacy and Electronic communications directive: EC 2002/58

The Privacy Directive⁴ complements the GDPR by addressing privacy in electronic communications, including the confidentiality of communications, use of cookies, and direct marketing. It is relevant for POWERUP's communication activities, website management, mailing lists, and online engagement tools.

1.3.1.4 Legal nature of data and IP issues: ownership, protection of database and trade secrets

EU legislation establishes rules on the ownership and protection of data, including database rights⁵ and trade secrets⁶. These rules safeguard proprietary information while enabling lawful data sharing. In POWERUP, data ownership, access rights, and confidentiality are regulated by the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, ensuring protection of background and foreground results.

1.3.1.5 Legislation on open data: (EU) 2019/1024

In addition to EU-level legislation⁷, each POWERUP partner complies with applicable national data protection laws that implement and complement the GDPR. These regulations may define specific procedural requirements, supervisory authorities, and enforcement mechanisms at national level.

The Directive provides that public sector bodies shall make their documents available in any pre-existing format or language, and, where possible and appropriate, in open and machine-readable format together with their metadata. Both the format and the metadata should, in so far as possible, comply with formal open standards. As the data processed under the POWERUP project can be produced by public bodies, we will need to understand if and how the mentioned legislation applies on these data and what are the relevant effects on this project.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>

² Free Flow of Non-Personal Data Regulation: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2018/1807/oj>

³ Data Governance Act – Regulation (EU) 2022/868: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/868/oj>

⁴ Directive 2002/58/EC <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0058>

⁵ Directive 96/9/EC <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31996L0009>

⁶ Directive (EU) 2016/943 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/943/oj>

⁷ Directive (EU) 2019/1024 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj/eng>

1.3.1.6 National data protection regulations

In addition to EU-level legislation⁸, each POWERUP partner complies with applicable national data protection laws that implement and complement the GDPR. These regulations may define specific procedural requirements, supervisory authorities, and enforcement mechanisms at national level.

1.3.1.7 Cybersecurity regulations and risk management

EU cybersecurity legislation establishes measures to ensure a high common level of network and information security across the Union. These rules support risk management, incident reporting, and protection of digital systems. POWERUP applies appropriate cybersecurity practices to safeguard data and digital tools used in the project.

1.3.2 Ethical Guidelines and best practices

POWERUP adheres to recognised EU ethical standards for research and innovation. Ethical principles guide stakeholder engagement, data use, inclusiveness, and responsible innovation, ensuring respect for fundamental rights and societal values.

1.3.2.1 AI and data ethics

POWERUP applies EU ethical and regulatory principles⁹ for the responsible use of AI and data analytics. The project does not develop or deploy high-risk AI systems; however, all data-driven and analytical tools are designed in line with the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, ensuring human oversight, transparency, fairness, robustness, and accountability.

With AI playing a growing role in research, ethical guidelines are needed to ensure responsible AI development. POWERUP takes into account the EU Artificial Intelligence Act¹⁰, adopting a risk-based and proportionate approach to governance and transparency. Data analytics activities rely primarily on aggregated, anonymised, and non-personal data, minimising ethical and legal risks while supporting responsible and trustworthy innovation. This also includes:

- EU Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI which focuses on emphasising transparency, human oversight, accountability, and fairness.
- Non-Discrimination and Bias Mitigation which focuses on ensuring AI models do not reinforce biases or lead to unfair treatment.
- Explainability and Interpretability which focuses on providing clear documentation on AI decision-making processes.

⁸ Framework of EU data protection https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/data-protection-eu_en

⁹ EU ethical and regulatory principles <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj/eng>

1.3.2.2 *Ethical Research involving Humans*

Research involving human participants must respect dignity, autonomy, and rights. This includes voluntary participation, informed consent, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw. POWERUP applies these principles¹¹ in all stakeholder engagement and participatory activities.

1.3.2.3 *Gender equality and inclusivity*

Gender equality and inclusiveness are core EU values integrated¹² into research and innovation. POWERUP promotes balanced participation, avoids bias in data collection and analysis, and ensures that diverse perspectives are considered.

¹¹ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/196377/AI%20HLEG_Ethics%20Guidelines%20for%20Trustworthy%20AI.pdf

¹² https://commission.europa.eu/topics/equality-and-inclusion_en

2 Data Management Plan (DMP)

The Data Management Plan reflects the nature of POWERUP as a Coordination and Support Action, where data processing activities mainly support analysis, stakeholder engagement, tool development, validation, and dissemination, rather than experimental or high-risk research.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) ensures that research data is managed responsibly, in compliance with FAIR principles, ethical standards, and legal frameworks such as GDPR. It outlines procedures for data collection, processing, storage and sharing, ensuring transparency, security, and sustainability.

2.1 Data summary

This section describes the types of data generated and collected in POWERUP, the procedures for managing such data throughout the project lifecycle, and the measures adopted to ensure compliance with data protection, intellectual property, and open science requirements.

2.1.1 Type and format of data that will be generated/collected

The main categories of data generated or collected in POWERUP include qualitative data derived from stakeholder engagement and regional inputs; quantitative and aggregated indicators supporting analytical and comparative assessments; aggregated geospatial and technical data used in decision-support and analytical frameworks; documentation and dissemination materials produced within the project; and audiovisual data generated during events and dissemination activities, subject to consent.

Qualitative data are generated through stakeholder engagement activities such as surveys, interviews, focus groups, workshops, consultations, and written contributions from pilot and follower regions. A clear distinction is made between fully anonymous data collected through surveys, which do not collect any direct or indirect personal identifiers, and pseudonymised qualitative data collected through interviews and focus groups, which require the temporary processing of minimal contact data for participation management purposes. All qualitative data are processed in anonymised or aggregated form for analysis and reporting.

Quantitative data consist mainly of aggregated indicators related to regional energy contexts, governance frameworks, participation metrics, and structured analytical inputs supporting methodological development and comparative assessments. Where relevant, aggregated geospatial and technical data from public or secondary sources are used within analytical and decision-support frameworks, without involving real-time or operational data collection.

Documentation and dissemination materials include project deliverables, reports, guidelines, presentations, training and capacity-building materials. Audiovisual data may include photographs or video recordings from events and dissemination activities, collected only with prior information and consent where required.

Data formats may include text documents (PDF, DOCX), spreadsheets (XLSX, CSV), structured databases, geospatial files, and multimedia formats.

Table 2. Data related to the Work Package

Type of data	Description
Stakeholder feedback (qualitative data)	Feedback from workshops, interviews, and co-creation sessions with public authorities, regions, and stakeholders.
Surveys (qualitative data)	Survey responses related to social acceptability, perceived fairness, governance frameworks, stakeholder perceptions, and project's open call for follower regions.
Written contributions (qualitative data)	Written inputs, comments, case descriptions, and qualitative assessments from pilot and follower regions.
Aggregated indicators (quantitative data)	Aggregated indicators related to regional energy contexts, governance structures, and enabling conditions.
Participation metrics (quantitative data)	Participation statistics and summary metrics from engagement, workshops, and dissemination activities.
Structured analytical inputs (Quantitative data)	Structured inputs used for analysis, scenario assessment, and decision-support methodologies.
Geospatial and technical data (aggregated, non-personal)	Aggregated geospatial and technical data used in GIS-based decision-support and analytical components.
Documentation and dissemination materials	Deliverables, reports, guidelines, presentations, training and capacity-building materials.
Audiovisual data	Photographs and video recordings from events, workshops, and dissemination activities (subject to consent).

2.2 Data management

Data management within POWERUP ensures that research data are handled responsibly, securely, and transparently throughout the project lifecycle, in accordance with the FAIR principles, ethical standards, and applicable legal frameworks, including the GDPR. As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), POWERUP focuses on the organisation, processing, storage, protection, and controlled sharing of qualitative, quantitative, aggregated, and publicly available data, without deploying technical infrastructures or collecting real-time or automated data.

Data are primarily generated through stakeholder engagement activities (e.g. surveys, interviews, focus groups, workshops, and consultations), desk research, and the use of existing public or secondary datasets. Data processing includes aggregation, anonymisation or pseudonymisation where applicable, and quality checks. Personal data are processed separately from research data, stored securely, and accessed only by authorised partners on a need-to-know basis.

Appropriate technical and organisational measures are applied to protect data against unauthorised access, loss, or disclosure. Data sharing follows the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,”

with non-sensitive and anonymised data supporting public deliverables and publications made openly available, while confidential or personal data remain restricted.

Limited personal data may also be collected through the project website (e.g. contact forms or event registrations), in accordance with the POWERUP privacy policy. Data retention and deletion measures, including the secure deletion or anonymisation of personal data at the end of the project, are defined in Section 2.2.8.

2.2.1 Participants and personal data

When collecting data from participants through surveys, interviews, or focus groups for research activities within POWERUP, all personal data are handled in accordance with the GDPR and applicable ethical standards. Prior to any data collection, participants are informed about the purpose of the activity, the type of data being collected, how the data will be used, who will have access to it, and their rights under GDPR, including the right to withdraw consent at any time without negative consequences.

Informed consent procedures are designed to be clear, transparent, and understandable, and consent forms are made available in the participants' native languages where necessary. Participants are informed about how results may be shared or published, with a clear explanation of anonymisation measures. A clear contact point is provided for any questions or complaints related to data protection or participation rights.

These general principles are implemented in POWERUP through specific data management procedures for surveys, interviews, and focus groups, as described below.

2.2.1.1 *Data collected from surveys*

Surveys conducted within POWERUP are designed to be fully anonymous. No direct or indirect personal identifiers, such as names, email addresses, phone numbers, IP addresses, or precise location data, are collected. Survey data are limited to non-identifiable contextual and segmentation variables (e.g. age group ranges, gender, education level, broad employment sector, or general area of residence) strictly necessary for analytical purposes.

Survey data are collected using GDPR-compliant tools hosted within the European Economic Area (EEA). Access to raw survey data is restricted to authorised project partners involved in analysis. Survey results are processed and reported exclusively in aggregated and non-identifiable form. Raw survey data are retained only for the minimum period necessary for analysis and reporting and are subsequently deleted or fully anonymised, in accordance with institutional policies and the Grant Agreement.

The informed consent form should be straightforward and understandable, available in the participants' native languages if necessary. Details about who will access the data, how it is controlled, and restrictions on its use should be specified, along with the data retention period and destruction procedures after its expiration. Plans for sharing survey results with participants or other stakeholders should be outlined, including any intentions to publish the data. Ensuring that data publication procedures are communicated to participants, with detailed plans for anonymization, is crucial. A clear contact point for participant inquiries or complaints should be provided to address any concerns about participation rights.

An example of the information that will be provided to participants in POWERUP surveys can be found in ANNEX 1. Informed consent form for participating in surveys.

2.2.1.2 Data collected from interviews and focus group

Interviews and focus groups conducted within POWERUP involve the collection of minimal personal contact data (name, affiliation or stakeholder category, and email address and/or phone number) solely for the purpose of organising participation and communication. Contact data are stored separately from research data and are never linked to individual contributions during analysis or reporting.

Audio recording of interviews and focus group sessions is carried out only with the explicit and informed consent of participants. Video recording is not foreseen unless explicitly required and agreed upon. Transcripts are anonymised by removing direct identifiers and by generalising potentially identifying contextual information. Participants are referenced using neutral labels, and no individual profiles are created.

Audio recordings are retained only for as long as necessary to complete transcription and quality control and are deleted once these steps are completed, and no later than twelve months after collection. Anonymised transcripts and analytical materials may be retained for reporting, audit, and scientific documentation purposes, provided that individuals are no longer identifiable. Results are reported exclusively in an aggregated and non-identifiable form.

2.2.1.3 Photography or filming in events

When photography or video recordings are taken of participants during POWERUP or external related events, special care must be taken to ensure that this visual data is collected and used in compliance with the GDPR. As these images and recordings often constitute personal data, particularly if individuals are clearly identifiable, it is essential to obtain explicit, informed consent before capturing or using any such material. This consent should clearly state the purpose of the recordings, how and where the images or videos will be used (e.g., in reports, on the project website, social media, or promotional materials), and who will have access to them. Participants must be informed of their right to refuse or withdraw consent at any time, without affecting their participation in the event.

Photography and video recording during events may take place for communication and dissemination purposes. Participants are informed in advance and consent is collected where required. Opt-out mechanisms are provided.

An example of Consent form for photography or filming participants in POWERUP events is on ANNEX 3: Consent form for photography or filming.

When filming or photographing in group, it's good practice to use signage at the venue informing attendees that recording is taking place and offering a way to opt out, either by notifying staff or sitting in non-recorded areas, where feasible.

Visual content should be securely stored, access restricted to authorized personnel, and used only for the purposes stated at the time of consent. If any material is to be made publicly available or used beyond the initial scope, fresh consent may be required. To protect privacy further, consider techniques like blurring faces or avoiding close-ups of non-consenting individuals.

2.2.1.4 POWERUP privacy policy

In EU-funded research projects, a comprehensive privacy policy ensures transparency and accountability regarding the collection, use, and storage of personal data. The POWERUP privacy policy should serve as a central reference point for all consent processes related to the project, including survey participation, photography and video recordings at events, email communications, and any other forms of identifiable data collection.

It clearly outlines what personal data is being collected, for what purposes, on what legal basis (e.g., consent or public interest), how the data will be used, and who will have access to it. The policy also provides information about data storage and security measures, any third-party processors or data-sharing arrangements, and the data retention schedule. The privacy policy informs participants of their rights under GDPR (such as the rights to access, rectify, delete, restrict processing, or withdraw consent) and explains how they can exercise these rights (via a dedicated contact email to the DPO). The policy will be easily accessible via the project website, linked in participant communications (e.g., consent forms, event invitations, online surveys), and is written in clear and non-technical language. Keeping this policy up to date and aligned with actual project practices is essential for legal compliance and building participant trust.

The POWERUP project website may collect limited personal data, such as contact details submitted through contact forms or event registrations. In addition, basic technical information may be collected through cookies, in accordance with applicable data protection and Privacy requirements.

All personal data collected via the project website are processed in line with the POWERUP Privacy Policy and Cookie Policy, which are publicly available on the website www.power-horizon.eu

These policies provide transparent information on data categories, purposes of processing, legal basis, retention periods, and users' rights under the GDPR.

2.2.2 Providers and proprietary data

In cases where data are provided by third parties or partners under specific conditions, such data are treated as confidential and used exclusively for the purposes agreed within the project.

Proprietary data is defined as follows:

- Data that embody trade secrets or are commercial or financial information that is confidential and privileged.
- Data that are not customarily released to the public.
- Data whose disclosure to the public could result in financial harm to the provider, to owners of buildings whose information is contained in the data, or to other stakeholders.

Confidentiality obligations are governed by the Consortium Agreement and, where applicable, additional confidentiality arrangements.

Both participant and provider data will be recorded only if they give their informed consent, accept the purposes of data use for POWERUP, and the registration of these data is relevant to the project.

2.2.3 Data protection and personal data governance

The responsibilities related to data protection within the POWERUP project are defined in Chapter 4.4 of the Consortium Agreement and are implemented in accordance with the provisions of the Grant Agreement, in particular those related to ethics, personal data protection and data management.

Where necessary, the project partners shall cooperate in order to enable one another to comply with the legal obligations arising from applicable data protection legislation, in particular Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (GDPR), as well as the relevant national data protection laws applicable to each partner.

These obligations apply to all personal data processing activities carried out within the scope of the implementation, management and administration of the POWERUP project, and in accordance with the roles and responsibilities defined in the Consortium Agreement.

Where required, and prior to the start of any data processing or data sharing activities, the project partners shall establish appropriate arrangements, such as data processing agreements, data sharing agreements and/or joint controller agreements, in order to clearly define roles, responsibilities and applicable data protection measures, ensuring full compliance with the GDPR and relevant national legislation.

2.2.3.1 Lawful Basis for data processing

The lawful bases for processing personal data may include:

- Informed consent.
- Legitimate interest related to the implementation of the project.
- Legal obligations arising from Horizon Europe reporting, communication and dissemination requirements.

The applicable lawful basis is determined on a case-by-case basis, depending on the nature and purpose of the processing activity.

2.2.3.2 Informed consent

Where consent is required as the lawful basis for processing, it is obtained in a clear, informed and documented manner, in accordance with GDPR requirements. Participants are informed about the purpose of the processing, the type of data collected and their rights as data subjects.

Participants may withdraw their consent at any time, without prejudice, and such withdrawal will not affect the lawfulness of processing carried out prior to the withdrawal.

2.2.3.3 Data minimisation

POWERUP applies the principle of data minimisation by collecting and processing only data that are strictly necessary to achieve the project objectives. Data collection activities are designed to avoid excessive or irrelevant information.

This approach reduces risks for data subjects and supports proportional and responsible data processing.

2.2.3.4 Legitimate interest

When personal data are processed on the basis of legitimate interest, POWERUP ensures that such processing is justified, necessary, and proportionate. The potential impact on data subjects' rights and freedoms is assessed and balanced against the project's objectives.

Legitimate interest is applied only where no less intrusive alternative is available and where the processing is compatible with the objectives of the Horizon Europe framework.

2.2.3.5 Data security and protection measures

POWERUP implements appropriate technical and organisational measures to protect data against unauthorised access, loss, alteration, or disclosure. These measures include access controls, secure storage, and restricted data sharing.

Security practices are proportionate to the nature and sensitivity of the data processed.

2.2.3.6 Data protection officer

Each project partner ensures access to a Data Protection Officer (DPO) or an equivalent function, in accordance with applicable national requirements. The DPO supports compliance with data protection obligations and acts as a contact point for data protection matters.

2.2.3.7 Roles: Data controller and processor

Each partner acts as data controller for the personal data processed under its responsibility within the project, unless otherwise defined through specific data sharing or joint controller arrangements established in accordance with the Consortium Agreement.

Where data processors are involved, they act exclusively under documented instructions from the relevant data controllers. Processing activities are governed by appropriate agreements ensuring compliance with GDPR requirements and adequate protection of personal data.

2.2.4 **Dissemination, open access and protection of results**

Each project partner shall ensure that its own results (foreground) are disseminated as swiftly as possible, provided that a prior decision regarding their potential protection has been taken, where applicable, through intellectual property rights (IPR) or other appropriate protection mechanisms.

Proper objection procedures and explicit consent mechanisms shall be applied in order to ensure that no partner publishes or authorises the publication of results, data or information that constitute foreground, background or confidential information belonging to another partner, without prior approval, in accordance with the provisions of the Consortium Agreement.

Public project deliverables containing non-sensitive results will be made available through the project website and appropriate open repositories, in line with Horizon Europe open access requirements. In addition, the consortium will actively encourage the dissemination of project results through international conferences, policy-oriented events and open access scientific journals with high impact and relevance to the project scope.

Where suitable open access journals are not available in a specific field, the consortium will apply the green open access model, ensuring that peer-reviewed publications can be accessed free of charge via repositories. The gold open access model will also be assessed on a case-by-case basis. Dissemination venues and publishers will be selected to ensure full compliance with Horizon Europe open access obligations.

The data and outputs generated within the POWERUP project can be categorised as follows:

- Scientific and policy-oriented publications.
- Public project deliverables.
- Datasets, analytical outputs, methodologies, tools and data models developed within the project.

2.2.5 Open Science and FAIR data implementation

As part of the European Union's commitment to Open Science, transparency and collaboration, the POWERUP project follows the EU Open Science and Open Data Strategy. This approach promotes responsible data sharing, transparency and collaboration across research, policy and regional communities, facilitating innovation through knowledge exchange and reuse of research outputs.

POWERUP contributes to EU Open Science initiatives by making its non-sensitive research outputs openly available through Zenodo, the open-access repository supported by the European Commission and integrated within the OpenAIRE framework. Zenodo enables the deposition of publications, datasets and other research outputs, while providing persistent identifiers (DOIs) and tools to link related outputs, thereby supporting compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) and maximising the accessibility and reusability of project results.

Furthermore, POWERUP has established a dedicated project community in Zenodo¹³, which serves as a centralised, open-access repository for public project outputs. This community functions as a digital archive for project-related publications, datasets, software, presentations and reports, ensuring their long-term preservation and accessibility for researchers, stakeholders, policy-makers and the wider public. Through Zenodo, project outputs are made citable, traceable and interoperable, in line with Horizon Europe dissemination and Open Science requirements.

The use of Zenodo also supports wider outreach and engagement by increasing the visibility of POWERUP results through integration with OpenAIRE, Google Scholar and other indexing services. In addition, it facilitates collaboration and knowledge sharing by enabling the research community to access, reuse and build upon project outputs. Impact metrics such as downloads, views and citations are monitored through the platform, supporting project reporting, impact assessment and demonstration of compliance with Horizon Europe dissemination obligations.

In parallel, POWERUP disseminates non-sensitive results through the project website and dedicated communication channels, including newsletters and social media, in order to further maximise the visibility, accessibility and uptake of project outcomes and to contribute to policy-oriented dialogue and best practice exchange in support of the energy transition.

¹³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/powerup-horizon>

Together, these tools provide the organisational and technical basis for implementing the FAIR principles described in the following subsections.

2.2.5.1 *Making data findable, including provisions for metadata*

All documentation and research outputs uploaded to the POWERUP Zenodo community will automatically be indexed and made discoverable through the European Commission's OpenAIRE infrastructure, ensuring maximum findability and alignment with EU Open Science requirements. The content uploaded to Zenodo is accompanied by structured metadata, which enhances the discoverability, accessibility and reuse of project outputs. These metadata include, among others, information related to authorship, affiliations, keywords, funding acknowledgement, licensing and persistent identifiers (DOIs), supporting compliance with the FAIR principles.

An example of the metadata generated through Zenodo deposition is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Zenodo's metadata generated

Type of metadata	Description
Upload type	Type of output (e.g. publication, deliverable, dataset, presentation, image, video/audio, software, other).
Identifier	Internal identifier or reference code used for versioning and traceability.
Version	Version number allowing updates and tracking of changes over time.
Publication date	Date of publication or release of the output.
Title	Official title of the document or dataset.
Authors	Authors or responsible contributors (project partners).
Description	Short description or executive summary of the content.
Language	Language(s) of the output.
License	Applicable license for reuse, where relevant (e.g. Creative Commons for public outputs).
Funding reference	Horizon Europe Grant Agreement number and project acronym (POWERUP).
Contributors	Contributing partners or organisations.
Keywords	Keywords supporting thematic classification and findability.

All uploaded documents and materials within the POWERUP project are accompanied by descriptive keywords that reflect their content and thematic scope. Keywords are used to improve findability, thematic classification and retrieval of project outputs across internal data management tools and dissemination channels.

POWERUP has defined an initial, flexible set of general keywords, which can be adapted and applied to deliverables, publications, datasets and other project materials according to their specific objectives, target audiences and methodological focus. This keyword set may be further refined during the project lifecycle as new outputs are generated.

Table 4. Zenodo's metadata overview

Type of metadata	Description
By objective	Renewable energy uptake, Social acceptability, Energy transition, Territorial planning, Governance frameworks, Policy support, Replicability and scalability
By target audience	Regional authorities, Local administrations, Policy-makers, Energy agencies, Stakeholders, Citizens, Research community
By methodological focus	Decision-support tools, Participatory processes, Co-creation, GIS-based analysis, Scenario assessment, Multi-criteria analysis
By thematic area	Renewable energy sources (RES), Spatial planning, Energy communities, Citizen engagement, Regulatory frameworks

2.2.5.2 Making data accessible

All project documentation, including public deliverables, datasets, scientific publications and data models generated within POWERUP, will be deposited in the project's dedicated Zenodo community and made openly available, in line with the Horizon Europe Open Access and Open Science requirements.

However, a limited number of deliverables are classified as Sensitive (SEN) in the Grant Agreement due to their content related to internal project management, data collection methodologies, market uptake strategies or exploitation planning. These deliverables will be subject to restricted access and will be made available only to authorised project partners and European Commission officers, in accordance with the conditions set out in the Grant Agreement. The sensitive deliverables relevant to this section are:

- D1.3 Project Management Plan, first version,
- D1.4 Project Management Plan, second version,
- D2.5 Project Management Plan, final version,
- D3.1 Definition of data collection approaches and framework,
- D5.1 Integrated GIS datasets,
- D6.1 Description of the market uptake plan in Spain,
- D6.2 Description of the market uptake plan in Italy,
- D6.3 Description of the market uptake plan in Portugal,
- D6.4 Description of the market uptake plan in Greece,
- D7.1 Initial exploitation plan and sustainability strategy,
- D7.2 Final exploitation plan and sustainability strategy.

All other deliverables classified as Public (PU) in the Grant Agreement will be made openly accessible through Zenodo in accordance with the principle "*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*".

In addition, datasets that include geographically detailed, locally contextualised or otherwise sensitive information, such as datasets linked to specific regions, pilot areas or stakeholder groups, will be subject to restricted access. Ensuring the confidentiality of such data is essential in order to prevent the disclosure of sensitive, commercially relevant or context-specific information that could negatively affect participating regions, authorities or stakeholders.

For this reason, open access to POWERUP data will be limited to aggregated datasets or data that have been irreversibly anonymised, ensuring that individual entities, locations or contributors cannot be identified. Non-anonymised data will be used exclusively within the project for clearly defined analytical, validation and assessment purposes, and will not be shared with third parties or reused beyond the scope of the project.

Finally, selected data collected through anonymous surveys or stakeholder consultations may be made publicly available through the open-access repository in an edited and aggregated form, ensuring full compliance with ethical standards, data protection legislation and the FAIR principles.

2.2.5.3 *Making data interoperable*

POWERUP will support data harmonisation and interoperability by using common data models and standard terminologies where appropriate, ensuring that data from different sources can be compared and reused across work packages and regions.

All public deliverables and documentation produced within the project will be deposited in the POWERUP Zenodo community. Data and metadata published on Zenodo use standard and widely accepted formats, enabling interoperability with other repositories and platforms.

In line with the FAIR principles, POWERUP will use standardised vocabularies and persistent identifiers for licences, funding information and related outputs. Metadata will include qualified references to associated datasets and publications through resolvable identifiers, ensuring that project outputs remain findable, accessible and reusable over time.

2.2.5.4 *Making data re-use*

POWERUP encourages the reuse of non-sensitive and anonymised data by providing adequate documentation, metadata and clearly defined usage conditions. Data reuse is supported where it does not conflict with confidentiality obligations, intellectual property rights or the legitimate interests of project partners and third parties.

This approach supports responsible and meaningful reuse of project data in line with the FAIR principles and the objectives of the Horizon Europe framework.

2.2.6 Intellectual property rights

Intellectual property rights (IPR) within POWERUP are managed in accordance with the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. This framework ensures a clear distinction between background and foreground intellectual property, while enabling appropriate access, dissemination, and exploitation of project results in line with contractual and legal obligations.

2.2.6.1 *Background IPR*

Background intellectual property refers to any data, knowledge, or assets that partners bring into the project prior to its start. Such background remains the exclusive property of the respective partners. Its use within POWERUP is subject to the access rights and conditions defined in the Consortium Agreement and any relevant contractual arrangements.

2.2.6.2 Foreground results and IPR from the project

Results and intellectual property generated within POWERUP (foreground) are owned by the partners that generate them, in line with the Grant Agreement. Foreground IPR is managed to enable dissemination, exploitation, and reuse, while protecting legitimate interests.

2.2.6.3 Access rights and confidentiality

Access rights to background and foreground data are granted on a need-to-know basis and under the conditions defined in the Consortium Agreement. Confidential information is protected against unauthorised disclosure throughout and beyond the project duration.

2.2.7 Licenses

The selection and application of licences within POWERUP will be assessed on a case-by-case basis, in close coordination with the Project Coordinator, the partners responsible for intellectual property management and the partners concerned. Licensing decisions will take into account the nature of the research outputs, their intended use, exploitation potential and the Horizon Europe Open Science and Open Access requirements.

POWERUP will primarily make use of the following licensing schemes:

- Creative Commons (CC) licences¹⁴, which provide a flexible framework for granting copyright permissions to research outputs such as publications, reports, datasets and other non-software materials. Depending on the nature of the output and the intended level of openness, POWERUP may apply permissive licences such as CC BY or CC0 to maximise reuse, or more restrictive licences such as CC BY-NC where commercial reuse needs to be limited. The choice of licence will follow the principle *“as open as possible, as closed as necessary”* and will always ensure proper attribution of authorship.
- European Union Public Licence (EUPL)¹⁵, which will be considered for software, tools or digital components developed within POWERUP. The EUPL is a copyleft open-source licence created by the European Union and is particularly well suited to publicly funded projects. It supports transparency, reuse and interoperability, while ensuring legal certainty within the EU legal framework and compatibility with other open-source licences. Its use reinforces alignment with EU digital sovereignty objectives and supports the sustainable uptake and reuse of POWERUP tools across Europe

2.2.8 Data retention and long-term preservation

POWERUP defines data retention and long-term preservation measures in accordance with applicable legal, contractual, and operational requirements. Data are stored only for the period necessary to fulfil project objectives, ensure accountability, and comply with regulatory obligations, in line with the principle of storage limitation under the GDPR.

¹⁴ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/open-science_en

¹⁵ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/eupl/eupl-text-eupl-12>

Retention periods are defined according to the type and sensitivity of the data processed. Personal contact data and code keys linking participant identities to pseudonyms are retained only for as long as necessary to manage participation, communication, and potential withdrawal requests, after which they are securely deleted. Audio recordings from interviews and focus groups are retained solely for transcription and validation purposes and are deleted once these activities are completed, and no later than twelve months after collection.

Fully anonymised datasets, aggregated analytical outputs, and documentation supporting reporting, audit, and scientific verification may be preserved for a longer period, up to five years after the end of the project, provided that individuals can no longer be identified. Preservation approaches ensure data integrity, security, and controlled accessibility over time, using secure institutional storage systems and appropriate organisational safeguards.

2.2.8.1 Public data (anonymous)

Public and anonymised data generated within POWERUP will be made openly available through the project's Zenodo community once the corresponding deliverables have been approved and accepted by the European Commission. In the case of scientific publications, the underlying datasets will be made available no later than the date of publication and will be linked to the relevant publication.

For public datasets not directly associated with a specific deliverable or scientific publication, data will be released following an internal assessment by the consortium when they are ready for publication, and at the latest by the end of the project.

All public data will be preserved and remain accessible via Zenodo for long-term reuse. Zenodo provides long-term archiving of research outputs and ensures that, in the event of service discontinuation, all content and metadata will be migrated to other suitable repositories.

2.2.8.2 Public data (non-anonymous)

Certain non-anonymised and confidential data generated within POWERUP are necessary for the proper implementation of project activities and, where applicable, for the continuity of selected project outcomes beyond the project duration. Such data will be stored and processed exclusively for project-related purposes and in accordance with the applicable legal, ethical and contractual frameworks agreed with the data providers.

Rules governing the storage period, use and deletion of confidential data will be defined in line with the project's exploitation and sustainability activities and will ensure full compliance with data protection requirements. Where confidential data are required only for project implementation and analysis, they will be deleted no later than six months after the end of the project. This additional period allows for the completion of scientific publications or reports prepared towards the end of the project.

2.3 Data anonymization and pseudonymization

POWERUP applies anonymization and pseudonymization strategies to minimise risks related to the processing of personal data. These measures support compliance with data protection principles, particularly data minimisation and privacy by design. The choice of technique is proportionate to the purpose and sensitivity of the data processed.

2.3.1 Anonymization strategies

Suppression removes specific identifiers so sensitive fields entirely for instance names, phone numbers or exact geolocation.

Data Masking replace sensitive data with randomized values that retain the data format. An example of this practice is replacing names with asterisks or generic labels like “user123”.

Generalisation reduces the precision of data to make individuals less identifiable. An example of this practice is replacing exact ages with age ranges or full addresses with city level information.

Aggregation combines data into groups to avoid individual-level tracking. An example of this practice is reporting average energy use per building instead of per household or grouping data into broader categories to prevent identification.

2.3.2 Pseudonymization strategies

Pseudonymisation techniques will be used to handle personal data while still needing to track individual behaviour or performance over time, especially for datasets that require continued data linkage while protecting identities:

- Tokenization replaces personal identifiers with a random token or code that has no direct meaning.
- Encryption transforms identifiable data using a reversible algorithm with a secret key that allows secure re-identification if authorised.
- Key-coding mechanisms – Allowing only authorized personnel to re-identify data.

Pseudonymized data is still subject to GDPR protections, meaning access controls and secure storage are required.

3 Ethical research framework

Ethics is an integral component of research throughout its entire lifecycle, and ethical compliance is considered essential to achieving excellence in all research and innovation activities funded by the European Union. In accordance with Article 19 of Regulation EU 2021/69516, all activities carried out under Horizon Europe must comply with fundamental ethical principles and with relevant national, Union and international legislation, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and the European Convention on Human Rights and its Supplementary Protocols.

POWERUP adheres to the principles set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, including reliability, honesty, respect and accountability. All partners commit to conducting project activities in line with high standards of scientific and professional integrity, ensuring the quality, credibility and societal relevance of project outputs. These principles apply to all stages of the project, including data collection, analysis, reporting and dissemination. Research misconduct, such as fabrication, falsification or plagiarism, is explicitly excluded, and partners are responsible for ensuring that their internal procedures are aligned with these standards.

The POWERUP project is designed to deliver societal and policy-oriented benefits in support of the energy transition and does not involve activities that interfere with fundamental rights related to human dignity, animal welfare or environmental protection. Nevertheless, ethical compliance remains a cornerstone of the project, particularly with regard to the handling of data, the involvement of stakeholders and citizens, and the use of digital tools and analytical methods.

Ethical research conduct within POWERUP implies the systematic application of ethical principles and legal requirements across all relevant domains of research. The project follows the Horizon Europe Ethics Appraisal Procedure, which includes ethical assessment and monitoring before and during project implementation. Throughout the project duration, particular attention is paid to the following principles and rights:

- The principle of proportionality,
- The right to privacy,
- The right to the protection of personal data,
- The right to the physical and mental integrity of a person,
- The right to non-discrimination,
- The need to ensure high levels of human health protection.

3.1 EU code of conduct for research integrity

All partners and participants involved in the POWERUP project commit to respecting the highest standards of research integrity, as set out in the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity. Compliance with

¹⁶ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/ethics_en

these standards is a fundamental requirement for all project activities and implies adherence to the following core principles:

- Reliability, ensuring the quality of research through robust project design, sound methodologies, appropriate analysis and the responsible use of resources.
- Honesty, in developing, conducting, reviewing, reporting and communicating research in a transparent, fair, complete and unbiased manner.
- Respect, for colleagues, research participants, stakeholders, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment.
- Accountability, for the research process from conception to dissemination, including its management and organisation, as well as for training, supervision, mentoring and the broader societal impacts of the research.

These principles guide all POWERUP activities and underpin the project's commitment to ethical excellence, scientific credibility and societal responsibility.

3.2 The principle of proportionality

The principle of proportionality is applied across all POWERUP activities to ensure that research methods, data collection, and stakeholder engagement are appropriate and not excessive in relation to the project objectives. Only the minimum level of data and interaction necessary to achieve the intended outcomes is pursued.

This approach reduces ethical and legal risks for participants and ensures that safeguards are proportionate to the nature, scope, and potential impact of the activities undertaken¹⁷.

3.3 Gender equality

The Horizon Europe programme promotes equal opportunities and gender balance in the implementation of EU-funded research and innovation projects. This objective is addressed by encouraging balanced participation of women and men at all levels of research and innovation teams, as well as within project governance and management structures. In addition, Horizon Europe requires participating organisations to have a Gender Equality Plan (GEP)¹⁸ in place as an eligibility condition, ensuring the implementation of structured policies that promote gender equality, equal opportunities and the prevention of bias in research and innovation activities.

POWERUP fully aligns with these requirements. All participating organisations comply with the Horizon Europe eligibility criteria related to Gender Equality Plans, and the project has integrated gender equality considerations into its team composition and governance structures from the proposal stage onwards.

¹⁷ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/ethics/self-assessment_en

¹⁸ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/gender-equality_en

Attention has been paid to promoting gender balance in both working teams and decision-making roles, in line with the EU's commitment to gender equality in science and innovation.

Throughout the project duration, POWERUP will continue to apply a gender-sensitive approach to its activities and outputs. In particular, gender balance and inclusive representation will be considered in:

- website content and online communication materials;
- promotional and informational videos;
- images used in social media, publications and dissemination materials;
- the organisation of events such as webinars, workshops and roundtables.

3.4 AI Ethics

POWERUP applies ethical principles for the responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI)¹⁹ and data-driven tools, in line with EU guidance on trustworthy AI. Although the project does not develop or deploy high-risk AI systems, AI-supported or analytical tools used within POWERUP are designed to support evidence-based analysis and decision-making.

Key ethical principles include human oversight, transparency, fairness, robustness, and accountability. AI-supported outputs are intended to assist, and not replace, human judgement, particularly in policy-relevant and strategic contexts. The project also takes into account the risk-based approach established by the EU Artificial Intelligence Act²⁰, applying transparency and governance requirements where relevant.

¹⁹ https://www.europarl.europa.eu/cmsdata/196377/AI%20HLEG_Ethics%20Guidelines%20for%20Trustworthy%20AI.pdf

²⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024R1689>

4 Conclusion

The POWERUP project has established comprehensive and coherent frameworks for data management, research ethics, and gender equality, all fully aligned with relevant EU legislation, standards, and best practices. To ensure compliance with data protection requirements, the project has implemented clearly defined data retention policies, along with systematic techniques for anonymisation and pseudonymisation. These measures guarantee the lawful, fair, and responsible processing of personal data while maintaining the quality and integrity of research activities.

The project's ethical framework is based on fundamental principles such as reliability, honesty, respect, and accountability. In alignment with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and the principle of proportionality, the project incorporates ethical considerations throughout all tasks and activities. Mechanisms are in place to monitor compliance and ensure that high standards of research integrity are consistently upheld during the project.

Gender equality is a core priority embedded in the project from the beginning. Special attention is given to achieving balanced representation in team composition and decision-making bodies, including leadership roles. This commitment is reflected in the project's deliverables, dissemination efforts, and communication activities, ensuring inclusive, gender-balanced representation across all public-facing outputs.

These frameworks create a strong governance structure for the implementation of the POWERUP project. They support ethical research practices, ensure secure and compliant data management, and promote equal opportunities throughout the project lifecycle. This document, along with the related procedures, will be reviewed and updated at months 18 and 36 in the deliverables "D2.2 Data and Ethics Management Plan and Guidelines Second Version" and "D2.4 Data and Ethics Management Plan and Guidelines Final Version," respectively. This review process will help maintain the document's relevance and ensure compliance with evolving regulatory and project requirements.

Annexes

ANNEX 1. Informed consent form for participating in surveys

This form is intended to inform participants about the anonymous nature of the survey and the use of collected data within the POWERUP project. It ensures that participation is voluntary and that all responses are processed in compliance with data protection and ethical research requirements, exclusively for research and analysis purposes.

Survey participation and data protection information

This survey is conducted within the framework of the POWERUP project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101235894.

The data controller responsible for this survey is the International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE), located at C/ Gran Capità, s/n, Building C1 – Campus Nord – UPC, 08034 Barcelona, Spain.

Contact email: powerup@cimne.upc.edu

This survey is fully anonymous. No direct or indirect personal identifiers — including names, email addresses, phone numbers, IP addresses, or precise location data — are collected. All responses are used exclusively for research and analysis within the POWERUP project and are processed and reported only in aggregated and non-identifiable form.

Survey data are stored securely on GDPR-compliant servers located within the European Economic Area and retained only for the minimum period necessary to fulfil research, analysis, and reporting purposes, after which they are deleted or fully anonymised.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may withdraw from the survey at any time without providing a reason and without any negative consequences.

I understand that all data collected are anonymised and cannot be used to directly identify me.

I consent to the use of my anonymous survey data for scientific research purposes, including publications, reports, and potential sharing with other researchers through recognised research platforms, in anonymised form only.

I confirm that I have read and understood the information provided above and that I voluntarily agree to participate in this survey under the stated conditions.

Participant name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

ANNEX 2. Consent form for interviews and focus groups

Please provide this form to participants before the interview or focus group begins. Ensure all sections are completed and signed to confirm informed consent. Keep the signed form securely for project records and data protection compliance.

Informed consent form for Interviews and focus groups

Date:

Project Coordinator/Institution: International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE)
Contact email: powerup@cimne.upc.edu

Introduction

This privacy policy explains how the POWERUP project funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and innovation program under grant agreement number 101235894, processes personal data in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). We are committed to safeguarding the privacy and rights of all individuals whose data we process.

Data controller

The data controller responsible for processing your personal data is:

Lead Partner Institution: CIMNE

Address: C/ Gran Capità, s/n, Building C1 – Campus nord – UPC, 08034 Barcelona.

Contact: powerup@cimne.upc.edu

Purpose of participation

I understand that my participation involves taking part in an interview and/or focus group for research and analysis purposes within the POWERUP project.

Data collected

For participation management, minimal personal data (name, affiliation or stakeholder category, and contact details) will be collected. These data will be stored separately from research data and will not appear in transcripts, analysis, or publications.

Recording of sessions

Interviews or focus groups may be audio recorded for transcription and analysis purposes. Recording is voluntary and will only take place with my consent.

Anonymity and use of results

Transcripts will be anonymised before analysis. Results will be reported only in aggregated and non-identifiable form. No individual profiles will be created, and quotations will not be attributed to identifiable persons.

Retention of data

Audio recordings will be deleted after transcription and validation and no later than 12 months after collection. Anonymised transcripts and aggregated results may be retained for reporting and documentation purposes in line with project requirements.

Data protection rights

I understand that I have the right to access, rectify, or request the deletion of my personal data, and to withdraw my consent at any time without negative consequences.

Contact

For any questions regarding data protection or my participation, I may contact the POWERUP project team. I understand that some images or recordings may be kept permanently once they are published and be kept as an archive of POWERUP project.

I have read and understand the conditions and consent to my images being used as described.

Name:

Signature:

ANNEX 3: Consent form for photography or filming

*This form is intended to obtain participants' explicit consent for the collection and use of photographs and video recordings within the framework of the project. It ensures compliance with data protection and ethical requirements regarding the processing, storage, and **dissemination** of visual materials for communication, research, and educational purposes.*

Use of photographs and video recordings

This consent form applies to visual materials collected within the framework of the POWERUP project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101235894.

The data controller responsible for processing visual data is the International Center for Numerical Methods in Engineering (CIMNE), located at C/ Gran Capità, s/n, Building C1 – Campus Nord – UPC, 08034 Barcelona, Spain.

Contact email: powerup@cimne.upc.edu

I hereby voluntarily consent to the taking, processing, storage, and use of photographs and/or video recordings in which I may appear, collected within the framework of the project.

These materials may be used for project communication, dissemination, educational, scientific, and research purposes, including but not limited to publications, reports, websites, social media channels, presentations, and training activities.

I acknowledge that content published online may be accessible worldwide and that data protection standards in countries outside the European Union may differ from those applicable under EU legislation. I further understand that certain images and recordings may be retained for long-term archiving in accordance with project requirements and applicable data protection regulations.

I confirm that I have been informed of my rights regarding the processing of my personal data and that I may withdraw my consent at any time without negative consequences, in accordance with applicable law.

Participant full name: _____

Signature: _____

Date: _____

More information: www.powerup-horizon.eu

Funded by
the European Union

Co-funded by the European Union, under Grant Agreement nº 101235894. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.